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Recommendation for ratcheting rules

for P91 components

D. 4.4

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Summary

This report constitutes the final deliverable D4.4 – «Recommendation for ratcheting rules for P91 components» of task 4.2 «Ratcheting rules for P91» of the MATTER Project. The objective of this task was to investigate the limits of design rules contained in present-day nuclear Codes & Standards (C&S) with respect to the mechanical behaviour of the ferritic-martensitic 9%Cr steel P91. The objectives of the work performed in this report were: i) compare the results of numerical simulation with uniaxial-ratcheting experiments performed within the matter project; ii) develop a structural test for the analysis of thermal ratcheting in a configuration relevant for Gen IV reactors vessels and iii) proposal of an improved rule based on the efficiency diagram method in order to effectively prevent ratcheting in P91 components.

All objectives have been achieved as presented in the report. The simulation ability of the new developed constitutive model for P91 is proved to be satisfying. The experimental campaign has provided carefully obtained ratcheting data to be used as verification and validation benchmark of inelastic finite elements models. A new efficiency diagram rule is proposed for 9Cr steels including a specific efficiency diagram and corresponding limits taking into account the softening behaviour of the material.

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1 Introduction

This report constitutes the final deliverable D4.4 – «Recommendation for ratcheting rules for P91 components» of task 4.2 «Ratcheting rules for P91» of the MATTER Project. The objective of this task was to investigate the limits of design rules contained in present-day nuclear Codes & Standards (C&S) with respect to the mechanical behaviour of the ferritic-martensitic 9%Cr steel P91.

Modified 9Cr-1Mo steels are being considered as structural material for several components in fourth generation and fusion power plants because they present good thermo-physical properties, excellent stability under neutron irradiation and good creep strength up to 550°C. These components will experience strong thermally induced strain cycling during the operation of the reactor. However, with respect to austenitic steels, 9%Cr steels present a very limited strain-hardening capability and soften under cyclic loads. Qualification of the material comprises therefore the verification of design rules contained in present-day C&S, in particular for type S (cyclic) damage modes like ratcheting and fatigue.

In the RCC-MRx code, the design assessment against ratcheting is performed by applying a simplified method based on the finite elements elastic analysis of the structure. The design rule uses a diagram called efficiency diagram, elaborated on the basis of the results of traction/torsion experiments. It consists in determining an effective primary stress P_{eff} which, if applied alone in the same condition of time and temperature, would lead to the same accumulated strain obtained by the application of a constant primary stress P combined with the cyclic secondary stress.

The goals of WP4 were: a) collect the data available in literature concerning the ratcheting behaviour of P91; b) perform a review of design rules contained in nuclear C&S to assess differences, limits and applicability to P91 steel; c) compare the results of numerical simulation with uniaxial-ratcheting experiments performed within the matter project; d) develop a structural test for the analysis of thermal ratcheting in a configuration relevant for Gen IV reactors vessels and e) proposal of an improved rule based on the efficiency diagram method in order to effectively limit ratcheting in P91 components. The first two objectives have been reached as reported in the previous MATTER deliverable D4.3 – «Review of existing rules for ratcheting». This report presents the results of the remaining activities and is organized in 3 parts, each one contained in a separate chapter:

- Chapter 2: Isothermal Ratcheting Behavior of the Ferritic-Martensitic Steel P91.
The isothermal ratcheting behavior of the 9%-Cr-1%-Mo ferritic-martensitic (FM) steel P91 is investigated by uniaxial cyclic loading tests at room temperature (RT) and 550°C. A unified visco-plastic deformation model taking into account the complex non-saturating cyclic softening of RAFM steels is further modified to adapt the ratcheting behaviour of P91. The simulation ability of the new developed constitutive model is proved to be satisfying.
- Chapter 3: Development of a structural test under cyclic thermal loading for the analysis of the ratcheting rules for P91 components.

The aim of the experimental campaign has been the development of a structural test under cyclic thermal loading for the analysis and assessment of the existing ratcheting rules in RCC-MRx and for the validation of the updated rules elaborated in the frame of the MATTER Project for P91 components. The experimental campaign has provided also carefully obtained ratcheting data to be used as verification and validation benchmark of inelastic finite elements models. After the description of the experimental facility, the experimental results are presented. Finally an evaluation of progressive deformation on an elastic basis, according to the RCC-MRx efficiency diagram is given.

- Chapter 4: Improvement of the efficiency diagram rule in RCC-MRx for P91 steels.
On the basis of the tension-torsion ratcheting tests performed task 7.3, the points corresponding to the experimental results have been represented in the space of the variables SR and V in order to determine, as a lower envelope of the most penalising tests, a new efficiency diagram for 9%Cr steels. The adaptation of the efficiency diagram criterion to 9%Cr steels implies also the definition of appropriate limits for P_{eff} . This is achieved by comparison with the $3S_m$ rule as defined for austenitic steels, but taking into account the softening behaviour of P91.

A summary and overall conclusions are provided at the end of the report.

2 Isothermal Ratcheting Behavior of the Ferritic-Martensitic Steel P91

The isothermal ratcheting behavior of the 9%-Cr-1%-Mo ferritic-martensitic (FM) steel P91 is investigated by uniaxial cyclic loading tests at room temperature (RT) and 550°C. Accumulation rates of strains (ratcheting rates) under multiple loading conditions are recorded to build the database of P91 for the further application in generation IV fission reactors.

The planned uniaxial strain-controlled and stress-controlled tests at RT and 550°C are currently finished. The material under research shows obvious cyclic softening in strain-controlled LCF tests at both temperatures which is found to affect the ratcheting behavior of P91 steel under stress-controlled cyclic loading.

A unified visco-plastic deformation model taking into account the complex non-saturating cyclic softening of RAFM steels is further modified to adapt the ratcheting behavior of P91. The simulation ability of the new developed constitutive model is proved to be satisfying.

Another report focusing on experimental part has been already written for D7.1. Hence in the first section of this chapter, only several important points concerning the experimental part are summarized. The procedure, methodology and main results in the modeling approach are presented in the second section.

2.1 Experiments

At both RT and 550°C, strain-controlled LCF tests are firstly performed to evaluate the cyclic softening of P91. The reason of the evaluation of cyclic softening is that it can accelerate ratcheting. Afterwards stress-controlled ratcheting tests are performed which are grouped according to various influencing factors, including peak stress, mean stress, stress ratio and hold time.

Several main material features of P91 observed in the experiments are listed as following:

1. With the same mean stress, larger peak stress leads to higher ratcheting rate, both at RT and 550°C (see Figure 1).
2. Maximum ratcheting rate is reached with stress ratio of around $-0.95 \sim -0.9$; ratcheting rate is relatively negligible if stress ratio R is larger than around -0.6 ($-0.6 < R < 0$), both at RT and 550°C (see Figure 2).
3. Strain range of each cycle increases with increasing cyclic number due to cyclic softening, both at RT and 550°C (see Figure 3).
4. Positive ratcheting under symmetric loading at RT but negligible ratcheting under symmetric loading at 550°C. (see Figure 4)

a) mean stress 25MPa, at RT.

b) mean stress 25MPa, at 550°C.

Figure 1 Ratcheting observed in tests performed with the same mean stress and various peak stresses at RT and 550°C, respectively.

a) peak stress 500MPa, at RT.

b) peak stress 325MPa, at 550°C.

Figure 2 Ratcheting rates observed in tests performed with the same peak stress and various mean stresses at RT and 550°C, respectively.

a) mean stress 25MPa, at RT

b) mean stress 25MPa, at 550°C.

Figure 3 Strain ranges in ratcheting tests performed with the same mean stress and various peak stresses at RT and 550°C, respectively.

Figure 4 Ratcheting strain for tests performed with zero mean stresses and various stress amplitudes at RT and 550°C, respectively.

It is found that the material response to stress-controlled cyclic loading has a tendency to close the hysteresis loop. This tendency is much clearer in the case with hold time at compressive peak at RT, as shown in Figure 5: The change of inelastic strain during hold time is -0.080%, while the total inelastic strain increment (ratcheting) is only 0.003%. This means that the partial inelastic strain formed during the stress-changing process is 0.083%, which compensates most of the partial inelastic strain during the hold time. Therefore the ratcheting rate of the test with hold time at tensile peak is only around 5 times higher than that without hold time, and the test with hold time at compressive peak still has positive ratcheting at RT

Figure 5 Stress-strain hysteresis loops at the half lifetime of ratcheting tests performed with various hold times at RT.

2.2 Modeling

With the aim of predicting the material response to more arbitrary loading conditions, a constitutive model is developed based on the current experimental data.

According to a variety of features in all tests at both temperatures and based on the analysis of various influencing factors to ratcheting, 9 criteria are listed which the simulated results should fulfill:

1. Fitting on ratcheting strains under multiple loading conditions.
2. Fitting on experimental hysteresis loops.
3. Showing cyclic softening in strain-controlled LCF tests.
4. Larger peak stress leads to faster ratcheting.
5. Maximum ratcheting rate with stress ratio of around -0.9~0.95.
6. Positive ratcheting with zero mean stress at RT.
7. Higher stress rate $\dot{\sigma}$ leads to lower ratcheting rate and vice-versa
8. Hold time at tensile & compressive peak leads to higher ratcheting rate at RT.
9. Fitting on accumulation of strain at 550°C in ratcheting tests with hold times and in creep tests.

The approach is to develop a model with reduced complexity which means that the number of material parameters should be as few as possible but still allow the description of the phenomena mentioned above. From the engineering point of view, model with reduced complexity is more preferred and the task to fit on ratcheting strain has the highest privilege among all criteria.

After analyzing the experimental data and testing with already existing models, it is assumed that two back stress (BS) components can be enough to simulate the ratcheting behavior: one controls the simulated shape of hysteresis loop and the other one controls the simulated ratcheting strain. Since most previous modeling approaches basically originate by Ohno & Wang (OW) [1, 2], the OW I & II models are tested for fitting on experimental results. However, with only two BS components, it is impossible to fit on ratcheting strains with the OW models under the multiple loading conditions considered. Besides, the so-called RAFM model built in [3] has been proved to have good simulation ability for strain-controlled tests on EUROFER97 and F82H mod., however it dramatically overestimate ratcheting on P91, because it includes dynamic recovery rule by Armstrong-Frederick (AF rule) [4]. It is found that the main task in the modeling approach is to design a new dynamic recovery rule of BS.

Accordingly, a new constitutive model is developed: It is based on the unified deformation models by Chaboche [5-9], including the internal variable for cyclic softening introduced by Aktaa & Schmitt in the RAFM model [3]. The equations of the new proposed model are listed in Table 1.

$\varepsilon = \varepsilon^{in} + \varepsilon^{el}$	(1)
$\varepsilon^{el} = \frac{\sigma}{E}$	(2)
$\dot{\varepsilon}^{in} = \left(\frac{ \Sigma - k}{Z}\right)^n \text{sgn}(\Sigma) \text{ with } \Sigma = \frac{\sigma}{\psi} - \Omega$	(3)
$\psi = \psi_1 + \psi_2, \text{ with } \psi_1(t=0) = 0 \text{ and } \psi_2(t=0) = 1$	(4)
$\dot{\psi}_1 = -h \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} $	(5)
$\dot{\psi}_2 = c \left(1 - \psi_{s,\infty} - \psi_2\right) \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} - r_\psi \psi_2 - \psi_r ^{m_\psi - 1} (\psi_2 - \psi_r)$	(6)
$\Omega = \Omega_1 + \Omega_2$	(7)
$\dot{\Omega}_1 = H_1 \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} - C_1 \Omega_1 \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} - R_1 \Omega_1 ^{m_1 - 1} \Omega_1$	(8)
$\dot{\Omega}_2 = H_2 \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} - \Omega_2 ^{n_2 - 1} \Omega_2 \left\langle \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} \frac{\Omega_2}{r_2} + \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} \mu_2 \right\rangle - R_2 \Omega_2 ^{m_2 - 1} \Omega_2$	(9)

Table 1 Constitutive equations of the new developed model for P91

The BS is composed of two sub-components: one follows the AF rule [4] and the other one includes the new designed dynamic recovery rule.

The evolutions of the two BS components with increasing inelastic strain are shown in Figure 6. As it can be seen, the BS1 oscillates around 0MPa since it follows AF rule and has a large modulus of dynamic recovery; while the BS2 oscillates around 25MPa, which is the mean stress of the applied stress controlled loading. It has smaller modulus of dynamic recovery, which can compensate most effect of asymmetry of external loading leaving only a tiny increment of inelastic strain (ratcheting) in each loading cycle. As a result, the model with BS2 can avoid the disadvantage of overestimating ratcheting of the AF rule, and the model can show the tendency to close the simulated hysteresis loops, as the material response does.

Figure 6 Back stress components in the new developed model for the test simulated at RT with $\sigma_{peak}=500\text{MPa}$, $\sigma_{mean}=25\text{MPa}$, stress rate $\pm 50\text{MPa/s}$.

Different candidates for the equation of dynamic recovery of BS2 are tested for multiple loading conditions, by fitting the parameter values for each of them. In the end, eq.(9) in Table 1 is selected for BS2 having the best performance in simulation.

Note that by selecting from different candidates for BS2, the following eq.(10) yields similar result as eq.(9).

$$\dot{\Omega}_2 = H_2 \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} - |\Omega_2|^{n_2-1} \Omega_2 \left| \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} \frac{\Omega_2}{r_2} + \dot{\varepsilon}^{in} \mu_2 \right| - R_2 |\Omega_2|^{m_2-1} \Omega_2 \quad (10)$$

From the mechanical point of view, application of the Macaulay bracket $\langle x \rangle$ (eq.(9)) instead of the absolute value (eq.(10)) is more reasonable, because the dynamic recovery is supposed to occur when BS and increment of inelastic strain having the same direction.

The parameters ($E, k, Z, n, h, c, r_\psi, \psi_r, m_\psi, \Psi_{s,\infty}, H_1, C_1, R_1, m_1, H_2, r_2, R_2, m_2, n_2$) are fitted using a program named MINUIT developed at CERN which uses variable-metric method with inexact line search to find the minimum of functions [10]. For RT, $n_2=1$ in eq.(9) for simplicity, $r_\psi=0$ and $R_1 \& R_2=0$ neglecting static recovery of cyclic softening and kinematic hardening, respectively. Accordingly, the model parameters for RT are reduced to the following ones: $E, k, Z, n, h, c, \Psi_{s,\infty}, H_1, C_1, H_2, r_2, \mu_2$.

For 550°C, $\mu_2=0$ due to symmetric material strength under tension and compression.

The comparison between model response and material response are presented in the following diagrams. All markers indicate experimental data and all curves indicate model responses.

The new developed model is able to simulate material responses under multiple loading conditions, including:

1. Fitting on hysteresis loops in strain-controlled LCF (see Figure 7).

2. Fitting on two stages of cyclic softening in strain-controlled LCF (see Figure 8).
3. Fitting on ratcheting strains in tests performed with the same mean stress but various peak stresses (see Figure 9).
4. Fitting on the relationship of ratcheting rate versus peak stress in tests performed with the same mean stress but various peak stresses (see Figure 10).
5. Fitting on the relationship of ratcheting rate versus stress ratio in tests performed with the same peak stress but various mean stresses and showing maximum ratcheting rate at stress ratio of around -0.95~-0.9 (see Figure 11).
6. Fitting on ratcheting strains in tests performed with zero mean stress at RT, showing asymmetry of material strength under tension & compression (see Figure 12).
7. Fitting on ratcheting strains in tests performed with the same peak and mean stress but various stress rates (see Figure 13).
8. Fitting on ratcheting strains in tests performed with the same peak, mean stress, stress rate, but various hold times (see Figure 14).

a) at RT.

b) at 550°C

Figure 7 Comparison between model description and material response: Stress-strain hysteresis loops of the first cycles in strain-controlled LCF tests performed with various strain ranges at RT and 550°C, respectively..

a) at RT.

b) at 550°C

Figure 8 Comparison between model description and material response: Cyclic softening in strain-controlled LCF tests performed with various strain ranges at RT and 550°C, respectively.

a) mean stress 25MPa, at RT.

b) mean stress 25MPa, at 550°C

Figure 9 Comparison between model description and material response: Ratcheting strains in ratcheting tests performed with the same mean stress and various peak stresses at RT and 550°C, respectively.

a) mean stress 25MPa, average rates before maximum strain reaches 4% or cycle number until 2500, at RT.

b) mean stress 25MPa, average rates before maximum strain reaches 3% or cycle number until 10000, at 550°C.

Figure 10 Comparison between model description and material response: Ratcheting rates in ratcheting tests performed with the same mean stress and various peak stresses at RT and 550°C, respectively.

a) peak stress 500MPa, at RT. b) peak stress 325MPa, at 550°C.
 Figure 11 Comparison between model description and material response: Ratcheting rates in ratcheting tests performed with the same peak stress and various mean stresses at RT and 550°C, respectively.

Figure 12 Comparison between model description and material response: Ratcheting strains in ratcheting tests performed with zero mean stress and various stress amplitudes at RT.

a) peak stress 500MPa, mean stress 25MPa

b) peak stress 325MPa, mean stress 7.5MPa

Figure 13 Comparison between model description and material response: Ratcheting strains in ratcheting tests performed with various stress rates at RT and 550°C, respectively.

a) peak stress 500MPa, mean stress 25MPa

b) peak stress 325MPa, mean stress 7.5MPa

Figure 14 Comparison between model description and material response: Ratcheting strains in ratcheting tests performed with various hold times at RT and 550°C, respectively.

However, the new developed model yields much lower strain increment in pure creep tests and in ratcheting tests with 5min hold time at peak stresses, comparing to experimental data at 550°C. This can be explained by the fact that the hydraulic testing machine is not specially designed and necessarily suitable for creep tests. Consequently much more creep strain can be observed than that of a well-controlled creep test. This is verified by comparing the data from the current work and those reported in Kimura et al. [11].

In spite of the simulation of creep tests, the new developed constitutive model can have satisfying performance in simulation under multiple loading conditions, both at room temperature and at 550°C. As shown in e.g. Figure 10, the model is able to simulate ratcheting strain in a large range of loading at both temperatures, from the loadings yielding very high ratcheting rates ($>10^{-4}$) to the loadings yielding relatively negligible ratcheting rates ($<10^{-6}$). Besides, the model is able to yield negligible ratcheting under loadings with relatively high stress ratios R ($-0.6 < R < 0$) as the material does at both temperatures. Further, it is able to simulate ratcheting strains under loadings with various stress rates reflecting the visco-plastic behavior of the material observed experimentally.

Consequently, this new developed model is able to predict material responses under more arbitrary loading conditions, either strain- or stress-controlled loading. For instance, the simulation illustrated in Figure 10 can be extended to even lower loadings. As shown in Figure 15 a), according to the prediction of the developed constitutive model, the material shows negligible ratcheting when the peak stress is lower than 400MPa. For application at 550°C, according to prediction shown in Figure 15 b), ratcheting is negligible when the peak stress is lower than 275MPa. The non-zero value of the average ratcheting rate is only due to accumulation of mean strain in the initial cycles.

a) mean stress 25MPa, average rates before maximum strain reaches 4% or cycle number until 2500, at RT,.

b) mean stress 25MPa, average rates before maximum strain reaches 3% or cycle number until 10000, at 550°C.

Figure 15 Comparison between model description & material response and prediction of ratcheting rates until lowest peak stress 250MPa. Ratcheting rates in ratcheting tests performed with the same mean stress and various peak stresses.

Hence at RT (550°C), the failure of structure due to isothermal ratcheting effect is negligible (ratcheting rate <math> < 10^{-6}</math>) if the loading is lower than 400MPa (275MPa).

2.3 Final considerations.

The model developed is a powerful tool for reliably predicting the material ratcheting behavior of P91 under arbitrary loading conditions. Hence, it can be used to assess the safety margin in new ratcheting design rules for P91 among others for structural ratcheting providing proper verifications and justifications in addition to experiments.

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3 Development of a structural test under cyclic thermal loading for the analysis of the ratcheting rules for P91 components

This chapter presents the results of the thermal ratcheting tests on axisymmetric thin shells made of P91 steel, carried out in the frame of the task 4.2 of the DM2 of the MATTER project.

The use of Cr Mo steels started during the first half of the last century for conventional fossil fuel plants applications. The need to increase the steam temperature and pressure and, as a consequence, the efficiency of conventional boiler/steam turbine fossil power plants, pushed to the development of several generations of steels designed to have high mechanical performances at high temperature. Modified 9 Cr 1 Mo steel, designated T/P91 steel (Fe, 9.0 Cr, 1.0 Mo, 0.02 V, 0.08 Nb, 0.05 N, 0.40 Mn, 0.40 Si, 0.10 C) was developed during the 70's and has been used extensively in the power generation industry.

The excellent mechanical properties of this steel are due to its microstructure obtained with a normalization, i.e. heat treatment at 1050°C followed by air cooling at room temperature, and a temper heat treatment at 780°. The microstructure is typically fully martensitic with an high dislocation density and a fine lath structure, stabilized by vanadium-rich $M_{23}C_6$ (M=Cr, Fe, Mo) precipitates along the prior austenite grain boundaries and on martensite lath boundaries and a finely dispersed MX-type (M=V, Nb and X= C, N) carbonitrides within the laths [1,2].

Due to its superior mechanical properties, P91 has been considered for the evaluation of its use in several proposed Gen IV reactor concepts for out-of-core (pressure vessel, piping, etc.) and, due to its excellent swelling performances under neutrons irradiation, for in-core (cladding, wrappers, and ducts) components [1,2]. P91 has 10^5 h rupture strength at 600°C of about 100 MPa, high yield strength, low thermal expansion coefficient (at least 30% lower than austenitic steels) and high thermal conductivity. The former three properties make it extremely resistant to thermal loads and thermal fatigue, on the other hand when submitted to uniaxial cyclic loading in the plastic range with a non-zero mean stress, P91 is known to exhibit “material ratcheting” i.e. accumulation of plastic deformation [3,4].

Ratcheting occurs in structures due to the non-uniform distribution of the stresses, caused by the interaction of a primary load and a cyclic secondary load that can be mechanical or thermally induced. Even for structures that are designed to behave in the elastic limit, plastic zones may exist and under certain combinations of the primary and secondary loads, under cycling, there is the accumulation of plastic strain with increments at each cycle [5]. Accurate predicting the ratcheting response is particularly important in safety and fatigue life prediction because ratcheting can lead to catastrophic failure of the structures. The design of liquid-metal cooled fast reactor systems components poses important issues in this regard, because of the frequent thermal transients that can occur due to the good heat-transfer characteristics of the liquid metal coolant.

In the RCC-MRx code, the design assessment against ratcheting is performed by applying a simplified method based on the finite elements elastic analysis of the structure. The design rule uses a diagram called efficiency diagram, elaborated on the basis of the results of traction/torsion experiments. It consists in determining an effective primary stress P_{eff} which, if applied alone in

the same condition of time and temperature, would lead to the same accumulated strain obtained by the application of a constant primary stress P combined with the cyclic secondary stress.

A particular situation that has attained extensive interest, is that schematized by the progressive deformation of a cylinder that is cyclically subjected to a temperature gradient traveling in the axial direction with no primary loads applied. The situation is representative of the ratcheting due to the variations of the free level of the coolant on the reactor vessel of a molten metal reactor: during the operation the coolant level moves up and down cyclically and the walls of the reactor vessel are cyclically subjected to a traveling axial temperature distribution. The stresses exerted on the structure are mainly linked to the movement of the axial thermal gradient since at the free surface the primary stresses are low or negligible. However, despite the absence of primary loads, there is a risk of progressive deformation [6,7,8].

This is a known problem and in the past many studies and experimental programs have been undertaken in order to find reliable methods of structural analysis. The simplified methods of analysis proposed in the design codes were not directly applicable in this specific case where primary type stresses are null or negligible [9,10].

The application of a simplified analysis in RCC-MR to this case was made possible in the 90's after the work by J.M. Gatt and M.T. Cabrilhat that proposed a modification of the rule to extend the application of the efficiency diagram. The method is based on the calculation of the primary stresses not only on the basis of dead weight, pressure or moment loads but also taking into account that a fraction of the secondary membrane stresses acts as a primary stress [11, 12].

Aim of the experimental campaign has been the development of a structural test under cyclic thermal loading for the analysis and assessment of the existing ratcheting rules in RCC-MR and for the validation of the updated rules elaborated in the frame of the MATTER Project for P91 components.

The experimental campaign has provided also carefully obtained ratcheting data to be used as verification and validation benchmark of inelastic finite elements models.

After the description of the experimental facility, the experimental results are presented. Finally an evaluation of the risk of progressive deformation on an elastic basis, according to the RCC-MR 2010 efficiency diagram is given.

3.1 Experimental part

The experimental campaign has required the realization of a facility able to produce cyclic moving axial-symmetric thermal gradients on a P91 cylindrical structure, sufficient to induce thermal stresses in the plastic range.

A literature review and theoretical preliminary study have been performed in order to test the feasibility, equipment and methods of the experiment.

Various thermal loads scenarios have been considered, in particular:

- hot thermal shock by induction heating
- cold thermal shock produced by induction heating coupled with cooling by water or water aerosol
- hot liquid thermal shocks

Due to the high thermal conductivity, relatively small thermal expansion coefficient and high yield strength of the P91steel, producing thermal gradients so intense that the associated thermal stresses yield the material, while keeping the size of the experimental sample to reasonable values, revealed itself as a challenging task. The most promising option has been to produce the thermal loads by hot liquid thermal shocks and it has been opted to perform the experiment by dipping a cylindrical specimen in a molten eutectic mixture of sodium and potassium nitrides (NaNO_3 60%- KNO_3 40% melting point at 221°C and stable in air up to 600°C). A molten salt facility with the performances required by the experiment has been modified and adapted for the purpose.

The external diameter of the cylindrical specimen has been fixed at 406 mm due to the size of the experimental facility available. The parameters of the experiment have been optimized by FEM simulations: it has been performed a non-linear thermal transient coupled with an elastic analysis to approach the combination of variables that maximize the hoop stress. The variables considered have been the specimen speed during immersion, the temperature of the molten salts and the thickness of the cylindrical mock-up. A non-linear thermal transient coupled with an elasto-plastic analysis with the Chaboche model has also been performed in order to evaluate the ratcheting strain. Best results have been obtained for a cylinder with thickness of 4 mm, insertion speed of 1mm/s and a temperature of 570°C for the molten salts bath.

3.1.1 Experimental Facility

A schematic diagram of the experimental facility is given in Figure 1 a). The mock-up is mounted on a metallic frame equipped with a stepper engine that makes possible to move it along the vertical direction and control its position and speed. Each cycle is made of a thermal shocks obtained by immersing the cylinder in the molten salts pool at 570°C at a speed of 1 mm/s, then the sample is extracted and cooled to room temperature. During the immersion, a temperature field with axial symmetry travelling upward, is generated and, in correspondence a stress field. Each point of the cylinder experiences a tensile hoop stress field before the contact with the liquid surface followed by a compressive hoop stress field when below the liquid level (Figure 16 b) and c).

Figure 16: Schematic view of the experimental apparatus.

As described in the following section 3.1, the experimental facility has been improved during the experimental campaign in order to:

- limit the heating by the thermal radiation coming from the molten salts bath
- limit the temperature decrease of the salts at the entrance of the sample

both items causing a decrease of the intensity of the thermal shocks.

3.1.2 The mock-up

The mock-up has been obtained by cutting a commercial ASTM A335M grade P91 pipe produced by the JFE Steel Corporation and machining both the internal and external surfaces to the thickness of 4 mm. The height of the sample has been fixed to 410 mm in order to have a wide region along the vertical axis where the distance from the top and bottom of the sample was larger than the decay length L of the cylinder, that has the value of 69 mm, calculated according to the formula

$$L = \pi / \beta \quad \text{with} \quad \beta = \sqrt[4]{3(1-\nu^2)} / \sqrt{R_m t}$$

where R_m is the mean radius, t is the thickness and ν is the Poisson's ratio.

The sample has been instrumented (Figure 17) with 16 k-type thermocouples, laminated and welded on the external surface along the axial direction, about every 50 mm from the bottom edge of the shell to 200 mm, and at 265 mm and 350 mm in one side: four additional thermocouples have been welded at 110, 160, 210 and 275 mm. Diametrically opposed, along the axial direction have been welded 5 thermocouples, one at the bottom and at 100 mm, 150 mm, 200 mm and 265 mm to check the axial-symmetry of the temperature field.

Figure 17: Thermocouples scheme

During each thermal transient the temperature data have been recorded every 0.2 sec by an high speed data acquisition system.

3.1.3 Strain Measurements

The measurement of the deformations required to dismount the sample from the frame and the acquisition of its profile with a *scanning acoustic microscope C-scan* (Figure 18 a)). The C-scan apparatus uses the non-destructive ultrasound technique called 'pulse echo' to measure the profile of the specimen. An ultrasound transducer that acquires the distance from the sample's surface is mounted on a frame that allows the scan along the vertical direction. A rotating platform allows performing a complete 3D scan. The precision of the system is 10^{-3} mm for the radial measurement (distance from the transducer), an error of 0.1 mm for the axial repositioning and an error of 0.1° for the disk rotation. The first measurement, on the as-received sample, has been done with a *water coupled squirter* system and frequency of 15 MHz, the other measurements have been carried out with an air coupled probe operated at 1 MHz. During each measurement 72 circumferential points for 400 circumference scans along the vertical direction have been acquired.

The distance measured by the ultrasound sensor at each point is relative to the position of the mock-up on the rotating table. Different positioning of the sample on the rotating table introduce an error in the measurements made of a periodic component with period 2π and an offset. The periodic component of the error has been eliminated by averaging the circumferential measurements, the offset has been eliminated by assuming a null deformation of the upper part of the cylinder and imposing that all the profiles coincide at the top.

Figure 18: a) The C-Scan the scanning acoustic microscope. b) schematic diagram of the measurement system.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Thermal loadings

Figure 20 shows the time trend of the temperature of the molten salts during the immersion of the cylinder: during each cycle, the temperature of the salts decreased of about 20 degrees starting from the initial value. The temperature variation has been found in agreement with that obtained considering the energy exchange balance between the sample and the mass of molten salts.

Figure 20: Time trend of the temperature of the molten salts measured during the insertion of the mock-up

Figure 19: Time trend of the temperature of the sample during the first cycle recorded at different distances from the bottom of the cylinder

Figure 19 reports the plot of the time trend of the temperature measured by the thermocouples located at different distances from the bottom of the sample. The thermocouple labelled F1 is located at the bottom and the others at increasing heights according to the scheme of Fig. 02. All the recordings are characterized by a sudden temperature rise as the free surface of the molten salts reaches the quote where the thermocouples are located. Moreover, (red arrow) all the trends show that the temperature at which the contact with the salts take place, increases due o the heat diffusion in the steel and the radiation heating by the liquid and the hot parts of the facility. It is clearly shown a decreasing trend of the maxima of all the registrations (blue arrow) due to the temperature decrease of the bath, decrease that is more pronounced at the entrance of the cylinder. A tentative to homogenize the temperature of the bath by using an impeller made things worse: the wavelets produced by the impeller in the molten salts surface caused a dramatic drop of the gradient.

By subtracting the trend over time of the temperature measured by adjacent thermocouples and dividing by their distance we obtain a quite accurate evaluation of the axial temperature gradient at the various positions. Figure 21, Figure 22, Figure 23, and relative to the 1st,12th and 21th cycle, show the time trend of the gradient measured as above at various heights. The common features are the same outlined above, that are the decrease of the maximum intensity increasing the distance from the bottom of the mock-up due to the heat diffusion in the sample, heating of the sample by the radiation field from the molten salts and local temperature decrease of the molten salts at the entrance of the sample.

Figure 22 Time trend of the temperature gradient at the first cycle.

Figure 21 Time trend of the temperature gradient at the 12th cycle.

Figure 23: Time trend of the temperature gradient at the 21th cycle.

The graphs in figures, show clearly that increasing the number of cycles, the thermal axial gradient decreased from values around 25-28 °C/mm to values below 20 °C/mm.

The origin of the gradient decrease has been individuated as due to the heating by the thermal radiation coming from the molten salts bath and caused by the change of emissivity of the sample surface due to oxidation. During the first cycles, the steel surface had high reflectivity (Figure 24), while as the number of tests increased, oxidation turned the surface of the mock-up to an intense brown colour (Figure 25). As a consequence, the cylinder has been heated by the thermal radiation before reaching the molten salts surface and during the immersion.

Figure 24: As received sample

Figure 25: Sample after some cycles

The effect of the decrease of the temperature gradient has been the decrease of the stress field associated and, during the cycles from the 16th to the 50th, little residual deformations have been measured.

In order to fix the issues outlined above, it has been decided to upgrade the experimental system. Radiation shields have been realized and installed. It has also been realized and installed an additional heater at the entrance of the sample, to eliminate the temperature drop at the entrance. A schematic drawing of the shields and additional heaters is given in Figure 26.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 26: Inner radiation shield a) Outer radiation shield and additional heater (blue arrow) b) Schematic diagram of the shields installed c).

The upgrades of the system have shown a good performance and the temperature gradient produced by the thermal shocks returned to values similar to those observed on the non-oxidised sample at the beginning of the tests (Figure 27).

Figure 27: Trend over time of the temperature gradient at the 57th cycle.

Since the positioning system of the experimental apparatus was not fully automated, a small delay (few seconds) by the operators in positioning the sample over the aperture of the molten salts bath, caused differences up to 30 °C in the temperature of the sample before the entrance in the bath. The resulting temperature gradients have shown a certain variability with values in the range 25-28 °/mm.

3.2.2 Residual radial displacements

Measurements of the radial deformation have been performed at the 0th, 8th, 16th, 50th and at the 100th cycle. Data have been processed according to the procedure outlined in paragraph 3.3

Figure 28 shows the results of the scans with the C-scan. The vertical axis reports the distance from the ultrasound sensor and the horizontal axis the distance from the top of the sample, both in mm. The as-received sample is not perfectly cylindrical and the radius at the bottom is 2.2 mm larger than at the top.

Figure 28: C-scan results. Distance from the ultrasound sensor vs. the distance from the top of the sample

Figure 29: Residual deformation respect to the as-received sample after 8, 16, 50 and 100 cycles.

The graph in Figure 29 shows the residual deformation respect to the as-received samples. The radius of the mock up shrank progressively in the region interested by the thermal loads. The maximum shrinkage in the region not affected by the boundary effects, that is, at a distance larger than the decay length of the cylinder, is of the order of 0.45 mm.

Analysing Figure 28 it is possible to note that the shape of the profile relative to the as-received sample shows some differences compared to the shape of the curves relative to the measurements of the profile after the various cycles. There is the possibility that the differences are due to the release of residual stresses produced by the fabrication process and by the successive machining during the first cycles. Residual stresses release should not be considered for the evaluation of the total plastic strain due to the thermal cycling.

For this reason in the analysis of data, two values of plastic stain have been considered ad evaluated towards the existing rules for ratcheting.

The first, obtained considering the radius shrinkage respect to the as-received mock-up, that has a value of **0,22%**.

The second values of plastic strain has been calculated considering the total deformation at the 100th cycle assuming as baseline the profile at the 8th cycle and has a value of **0,10%**.

3.2.3 Tensile properties of the sample

In order to analyze the data and assess the validity of the existing ratcheting rules, as well to contribute to elaborate the efficiency diagram for P91, the trend over the temperature of the

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tensile properties of the steel have been measured. The results are reported in Figure 30, Figure 31 and Table 2.

Specimen	T (°C)	PM Max Force (N)	YS(Mpa)	UTS(Mpa)	U.E%	T.E. %	T.E. post mortem (%)	Reduction of Area (%)
g91_02_1	20	13722.0	546.1	693.3	8.2	19.9	20.2	73.2
g91_02_2	20	13719.0	547.7	698.7	8.6	20.9	21.3	71.9
media	20		546.9	696.0	8.4	20.4	20.8	72.5
g91_20_1	200	11968.0	483.3	609.5	6.3	16.8	17.2	74.8
g91_30_1	300	11266.0	463.3	576.1	5.2	15.2	16.0	75.9
g91_40_1	400	11004.0	449.7	562.7	4.9	14.8	15.6	70.7
g91_45_1	450	10461.0	442.1	532.8	6.0	20.3	20.8	75.0
g91_45_2	450	10568.0	437.5	536.1	5.1	17.8	18.3	74.1
media	450		439.8	534.5	5.5	19.0	19.6	74.5
g91_50_2	500	9456.0	418.4	483.5	3.8	20.2	20.5	81.4
g91_55_1	550	8171.0	382.2	414.5	1.6	21.0	21.0	87.8
g91_55_2	550	8177.0	380.7	416.4	1.7	32.4	32.5	88.4
media	550		381.5	415.5	1.6	26.7	26.8	88.1
g91_60_1	600	6685.0	320.5	340.5	1.1	23.9	24.2	93.2
g91_60_2	600	6512.0	319.5	330.3	0.9	24.8	25.0	93.3
media	600		320.0	335.4	1.0	24.4	24.6	93.3

Table 2

Figure 30: Yield strength at 0.2% offset vs. T.

Figure 31: Ultimate tensile strength vs. T.

3.3 Numerical Interpretations of the experimental test

3.3.1 Thermal analysis

The purpose of the thermal analysis has been the reconstruction of the axial and radial temperature profiles over time.

The analyses have been conducted using the thermal module of the CAST3M fem code, developed at CEA in Saclay [13]. For the mesh it has been used a rectangular isoparametric 8 node elements, 6 nodes in the thickness and one every 0.5 mm in the axial direction, for a total of 4920 elements and 16413 nodes.

To take into account the displacement of the molten salt free surface, and thus the space-time variation of the boundary condition on the specimen, it has been inserted inside CAST3M an appropriate procedure that, given the speed of descent of the specimen, evaluates the speed of advancement of the level relative to the specimen. Then at the current time are recalculated:

- the position of the free surface,
- the spatial profiles of temperature and heat transfer coefficients relative to the air and the salts side
- the additional conductivity matrix and thermal force matrix associated with the convective boundary condition.

The boundary conditions on the area immersed in the molten salt, takes into account strictly the temperature variation of the bath, while the values of the heat transfer coefficients used have been appropriately increased ($2300 \text{ W}/\text{°C m}^2$) respect to the values calculated with theoretical

assessments ($1400 \text{ W/}^\circ\text{C m}^2$), to account for the presence of additional convective motions, attributable to the current leaked from the electrical heating coils. For the part above the molten salt it has been always used a convective type condition, which however takes into account, in an energetically equivalent way, of the irradiation of the metal parts and the free surface, with the temperature and heat transfer coefficient profile, suitably calibrated through comparison with the temperature profiles experimentally detected on the test section. Not taking into account this energy exchange of the emerged part would have resulted in an improper stress increase on the cold side of the heat front.

The values of the thermal properties of P91, conductivity, density and specific heat have been taken from RCC-MRx A3.18S.2.

In the following figures (Figure 32 - Figure 36) we note the good agreement between the calculated and the experimentally detected profiles both for the temperature levels and for the dynamics of the front movement.

Figure 32: Comparison of the experimental and numerical axial temperature distribution at 50 s.

Figure 33: Comparison of the experimental and numerical axial temperature distribution at 100 s

Figure 34: Comparison of the experimental and numerical axial temperature distribution at 150 s

Figure 35: Comparison of the experimental and numerical axial temperature distribution at 200 s

Figure 36: Comparison of the experimental and numerical axial temperature distribution at 250 s

3.3.2 Mechanical analysis

The mechanical calculation has been performed using CAST3M mechanical module [13]. The analysis was conducted in linear elasticity, consistently with the requirements of the RCC-MRx standards in RB 3231. The Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio used in the calculations have been taken from RCC-MRx A3.18S.2. Regarding the thermal expansion coefficient, it has been found that the values reported in the standards are both lower than those available in the literature for the P91 steel. Moreover the values reported for the thermal expansion coefficient have been found not coherent with the values calculated from the density values tabulated in A3.18S.2, according to the formula:

$$\alpha_{20}^T = \frac{\rho_{20} - \rho_T}{\rho_T} \frac{1}{3(T - 20)}$$

Where ρ is the density and T the temperature in °C.

Therefore the values assumed in the calculations for the mean coefficient of thermal expansion at the various temperatures have been increased by a multiplicative factor of 1.14, compared to the values tabulated in A3.18S.2.

The mesh used for the mechanical analysis has been the same used for the thermal calculations. The calculation has been carried out with the structure constrained axially at the top and left free to move along the radial direction.

The axial profiles of the equivalent stresses according to Tresca, relative to the inner (rose line) and outer (red) surfaces at various times are reported in Figure 37-Figure 41. The graphs report also the local value of $R_{p0,2min}^t$ from RCC-MRx A3.18S.2 (black line).

Figure 37: Axial distribution of the Tresca equivalent stress for the internal (rose) and external (red) side at 20s

Figure 38: Axial distribution of the Tresca equivalent stress for the internal (rose) and external (red) side at 50 s

Figure 39: Axial distribution of the Tresca equivalent stress for the internal (rose) and external (red) side at 75 s

Figure 40: Axial distribution of the Tresca equivalent stress for the internal (rose) and external (red) side at 100 s

Figure 41: Axial distribution of the Tresca equivalent stress for the internal (rose) and external (red) side at 200 s

It was then programmed a post-processing module to linearize the calculated stresses at the level of various and representative supporting line segments, in order to calculate, at various times, the values of the bending and membrane stresses required by the RCC-MRx. The stress range at the nodes of the structure has been calculated using the maximum shear theory, in accordance with the requirements of RB 3224.4.4. In Figure 42-Figure 45 the components of the stress along the supporting line segments are plotted (hoop green, axial red, radial yellow, shear blue). It is possible to note that the radial and shear components have negligible values. The axial component

has a quite linear distribution along the thickness, so the non linear part of this component is negligible. The hoop component has a mainly membrane distribution.

Figure 42: Stress distribution along the supporting line segment at the height of 36 mm from the bottom at 42 s (hoop stress-green, axial stress-red, radial stress-yellow, shear stress-blue)

Figure 43: Stress distribution along the supporting line segment at the height of 60 mm from the bottom at 65 s (hoop stress-green, axial stress-red, radial stress-yellow, shear stress-blue)

Figure 44: Stress distribution along the supporting line segment at the height of 100 mm from the bottom at 103 s (hoop stress-green, axial stress-red, radial stress-yellow, shear stress-blue)

Figure 45: Stress distribution along the supporting line segment at the height of 200 mm from the bottom at 196 s (hoop stress-green, axial stress-red, radial stress-yellow, shear stress-blue)

3.3.3 Verification of the conservatism of RCC-MRx RB 3261.1.1 for P91

The verification of the conservatism of the ratcheting rule RB 3261.1.1 in RCC-MRx for P91 steel requires, a series of data obtained from both numerical calculations and experiments:

- The secondary stresses range ΔQ

- The secondary membrane stress \underline{Q}_m
- The maximum membrane stress $\text{Max}(\sigma_m)$
- The temperature corresponding to maximum \underline{Q}_m

3.3.3.1 Determination of $\underline{\Delta Q}$

The stress range $\underline{\Delta Q}$ is calculated by linearizing the stresses originated from the secondary load, along the supporting line segment according to RB 3224.5.5 and 3224.4.4:

$$\underline{\Delta Q} = \text{Max} [Q(t) - Q(t')]$$

Table 2 reports the maximum values per cycle for selected sections.

3.3.3.2 Determination of \underline{Q}_m

Table 2 reports the two values of \underline{Q}_m , the secondary membrane stress \underline{Q}_m , corresponding to the passage of the cold side and hot side of the traveling temperature distribution. The average temperature on the section and the corresponding time are reported also.

3.3.3.3 Determination of secondary ratio SR and the efficiency index V

The secondary ratio (RB 3261.1.1.1) has been calculated as follows

$$\text{SR} = \underline{\Delta Q} / \text{Max}(\sigma_m)$$

Where $\text{Max}(\sigma_m)$ is half the maximum of the secondary membrane stress σ_m in correspondence of the hot side. Since the secondary ratio SR results greater than 4, the efficiency index V is calculated as follows:

$$V = 1 / \text{SR}^{0,5}$$

3.3.3.4 Determination of the experimental efficiency index v

The experimental efficiency index v is calculated as follows:

$$v = \text{Max}(\sigma_m) / P_{\text{eff_ex}}$$

where $\text{Max}(\sigma_m)$ is defined above

$P_{\text{eff_ex}}$ is calculated on the basis of the total deformations measured e_p , according to A3.18AS.451 as follows:

$$P_{\text{eff_ex}} = C_0 * (R_{p0,2}^t)_{\text{ave}} * (e_p)^{n_0}$$

Where C_0 and n_0 are the parameters given in table A3.18AS.451, $R_{p0,2}^t$ is taken from table A3.18AS.41 and e_p is the experimental plastic strain.

As stated in paragraph 3.2.2, the comparison between the efficiency index V and the experimental efficiency index v is carried out for two values of plastic strain:

- the plastic strain e_p obtained considering the profile of the as received sample as baseline with a value of 0,22%,
- the plastic strain e_p obtained considering the total deformation respect to the 8th cycle as baseline with a value of 0,1%.

The corresponding values of $P_{\text{eff_ex}}(0,10\%)$, $P_{\text{eff_ex}}(0,22\%)$, as well as the values of the experimental efficiency index $v(0,10\%)$ and $v(0,22\%)$ are reported in Table 3 for all the sections.

3.3.3.5 Conclusions

As show in Table 3 for all the sections and for both values of plastic strain considered, the efficiency index V , calculated according to RB3261.1113, results always higher than the experimental efficiency index v :

$$V = \text{Max}(\sigma m) \frac{\text{Max}(\sigma m)}{P_{\text{eff}}} > v = \frac{\text{Max}(\sigma m)}{P_{\text{eff_sp}}}$$

Thus, it follows that $P_{\text{eff_sp}} > P_{\text{eff}}$, that is: the effective primary stress evaluated according to the rule results to be lower than the value calculated on basis of the actual deformations.

Based on the experimental results obtained in the present experimental campaign the rule RCC-MRx RB 3261.1.1 results to be not conservative when applied to assess the ratcheting behavior of P91 steel.

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Sec.Lev mm	$\frac{\Delta Q}{M}$ MPa	$\frac{Q_m}{M}$ MPa	Max(σ_m) MPa	θ_m °C	t s	SR	V	$P_{eff_ex}(0,10\%)$ MPa	v(0,10%)	$P_{eff_ex}(0,22\%)$ MPa	v(0,22%)
36	849	240		102	25,5	-	-		-		-
"		248	124	455	42	6,847	0,382	398	0,311	421	0,295
40	845	239		102	29						
"		246	123	457	46	6,870	0,382	398	0,309	420	0,293
60	812	251		116	48						
"		229	115	458	65	7,06	0,376	397	0,290	419	0,274
80	800	254		125	67						
"		222	111	458	84	7,207	0,372	397	0,278	419	0,265
100	785	249		133	86						
		217	109	459	103	7,202	0,373	397	0,275	419	0,265
150	751	238		142	133						
		208	104	455	150	7,221	0,372	398	0,261	421	0,247
200	724	230		148	180						
		200	100	441	196	7,24	0,372	404	0,247	427	0,234
250	702	222		143	226						
		195	98	445	244	7,16	0,374	403	0,243	426	0,230
300	401	199		126	270						
		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3: Synoptic table for the verification of the conservatism of RCC-MRXRB 3261.1.1 for P91

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4 Development of an improved efficiency diagram rule for P91 steel.

Modified 9Cr-1Mo steels are being considered as structural material for several components in fourth generation and fusion power plants [1,2] because they present good thermo-physical properties, excellent stability under neutron irradiation and good creep strength up to 550°C. These components will experience strong thermally induced strain cycling during the operation of the reactor. However, with respect to austenitic steels, 9%Cr steels present a very limited strain-hardening capability and soften under cyclic loads. Qualification of the material comprises therefore the verification of design rules contained in present-day C&S, in particular for type S (cyclic) damage modes like ratcheting and fatigue.

In this report, the efficiency diagram rule to prevent ratcheting, used in the RCC-MRx code [3], was investigated. Experimental tests in support of the development of an improved rule have been performed in the framework of task 7.1 - «Additional qualification experiments to allow codification on 9%Cr and 316SS» and are reported in [4]. On the basis of the obtained results, this report proposes a modification of the efficiency diagram rule in order to take into account the specific behaviour of 9%Cr steels.

4.1 Rules to prevent ratcheting in RCC-MRx

Ratcheting is by definition the accumulation of plastic deformation in structures subjected to cyclic stressing above the yield limit with a non-zero primary stress. When a structure is subjected to cyclic loading, it may show signs of permanent deformation at the end of the first cycle. During subsequent cycles the following cases may arise:

- Plastic adaptation (shakedown): the structure is said to be plastically adapted if, after a few cycles, its behaviour becomes elastic at every point in the structure.
- Plastic accommodation: the structure undergoes plastic accommodation if, after a few cycles, its behaviour, while remaining elastoplastic, is the same at each cycle. Plastic accommodation excludes the possibility of progressive deformation.
- Global plastic adaptation (overall shakedown): global plastic adaptation (overall shakedown) is the state of a structure which undergoes plastic accommodation and in which: plastic strain only appears in strain concentration zones whose dimensions are less than the length of the supporting line segments of the sections under consideration. In this state, the response of the structure is generally elastic and the development of plastic strain is inhibited by restraint ensured by the parts which remain elastic. The strain concentration effect depends mainly on geometry, loading and the material behaviour law.
- Progressive deformation: in the absence of creep and for purely elastic and plastic behaviour, the definition of progressive deformation or ratchet is easy. There is progressive

deformation if an increase of deformation appears at each cycle under the effect of cyclic loads. This phenomenon is different from adaptation in which, after application of a few cycles, the structure retains the same geometry. When creep is involved, and consequently the time-related phenomena, this type of simple definition is no longer adequate. In RCC-MRx, progressive deformation is used to designate the increase in the deformation due to loads caused by imposed cyclic deformations.

A detailed review of the rules used in present-day nuclear C&S to prevent progressive deformation has been performed in [5]. The rules used in RCC-MRx are briefly recalled and further explained in the following sections.

4.1.1 The «3Sm» Rule

By definition, the limit for which a material experiences no permanent deformation is the elastic limit. Since the elastic limit is extremely difficult to quantify in a practical way, the engineering yield strength S_y is usually assumed as corresponding to the elastic limit. It can then be shown that, for an elastic-perfectly-plastic material, the theoretical limit for which a structure cannot experience progressive deformation is when the sum of the primary stress ($\overline{P} = \overline{P_L} + \overline{P_b}$) and of the variation of the secondary stress ($\overline{\Delta Q}$) is less than two times the yield strength [6]:

$$\text{Max}(\overline{P_L} + \overline{P_b}) + \overline{\Delta Q} \leq 2S_y$$

Taking in to account the limited amount plastic deformation (0.2%) at the yield strength, the $2S_y$ limit is therefore conservative for any material presenting strain hardening. Since for austenitic stainless steels like 316L(N), the primary allowable stress S_m (at temperatures up to 150°C) as defined by the code is equal to $(2/3)S_y$, the above rule can also be expressed as:

$$\text{Max}(\overline{P_L} + \overline{P_b}) + \overline{\Delta Q} \leq 3S_m = 2S_y \quad (\text{austenitic steels, } T < 150^\circ\text{C})$$

Note that for $T > 150^\circ\text{C}$, S_m is defined as $0.9S_y$ and the $3S_m$ limit is less conservative than the $2S_y$ limit, which is justified by the high strain hardening capability of these steels and their cyclic hardening behaviour. For austenitic steels, this rule insures shakedown after a few cycles.

Also, in RCC-MRx the application of this rule is limited to the negligible creep domain, which for austenitic steels corresponds to temperatures below 375°C.

For 9%Cr steels like P91, however, S_m is defined from the ultimate strength (S_u) as $S_m = (S_u/3)$ at Room Temperature (RT) or $S_m = (S_u/2,7)$ for $T > 150^\circ\text{C}$. The maximum value $3S_m$ becomes then significantly less than $2S_y$:

$$\text{Max}(\overline{P_L} + \overline{P_b}) + \overline{\Delta Q} \leq 3S_m = S_u = 1.3S_y \quad (9\% \text{Cr steel, RT})$$

The $3S_m$ criterion for 9%Cr steels is therefore conservative but extremely severe, preventing plastic deformation even when the cyclic softening of the material is taken into account.

4.1.2 The Efficiency Diagram Rule

The efficiency diagram criterion used in RCC-MRx has been developed in order to allow a limited amount of the cumulative strain to take place without compromising the lifetime of the material [7]. By allowing a limited amount of plastic deformation to occur, this method is in principle less conservative than the $3S_m$ rule. The basis of the efficiency diagram is however empirical since it is constructed starting from experimental tests as a lower envelope of the worst results. It should therefore be validated whenever a new material is used, especially if the strain hardening behaviour changes substantially.

For the construction of the diagram when creep is not significant, the effective primary stress (P_{eff}) is defined as the primary stress that, when acting alone, would give the same strain on the monotonic stress-strain curve as the cumulative strain observed at failure with a superposed cyclic primary and secondary load. The results of experimental tests are then represented on the space of the two variables $V = P/P_{\text{eff}}$ (efficiency index) $SR = \Delta Q/P$ (secondary ratio), where:

-) P is the the equivalent primary (constant) stress
-) ΔQ is the equivalent elastic secondary stress range acting on the specimens.

The efficiency diagram is then constructed as the lower envelope curve representing the «worst» results in order to obtain a conservative estimated P_{eff} using $SR = \Delta Q/P$ (Figure 46).

The efficiency diagram presently given in the RCC-MRx code has in fact been constructed and validated starting from a considerable number of results of experimental test (tension-torsion, internal pressure-axial deformation, etc.), at different temperatures and with or without hold times (creep), but performed mainly on austenitic stainless steels (Figure 47).

Figure 46: Construction of the representative points starting from experimental results.

Figure 47: Experimental base used to construct the efficiency diagram presently in the RCC-MRx code.

Using the efficiency diagram, the limitation of the ratcheting consists then in defining an allowable value for the effective primary stress P_{eff} . This value corresponds to a maximum allowable cumulative strain than can be determined on the monotonic tension curve. The efficiency diagram

allows to express a limit on the allowable strain as a limit on the allowable stress that can be calculated starting from the results of elastic analysis.

In RCC-MRx, two limits on P_{eff} are defined for the primary membrane stress alone and the sum of the primary membrane and bending stress:

$$P_1 = \frac{Max(\overline{P_m})}{V_1} < 1.3S_m \qquad P_2 = \frac{Max(\overline{P_L + P_b})}{V_2} \leq 1.3 \times 1.5 S_m$$

Where V_1 and V_2 are the efficiency indexes corresponding to the secondary ratios:

$$SR_1 = \frac{\Delta Q}{Max(\overline{P_m})} \qquad SR_2 = \frac{\Delta Q}{Max(\overline{P_L + P_b})}$$

According to the code, for austenitic steels, setting the limit of P_1 to $1.3S_m$ means that, in the most unfavourable cases, a membrane strain of 1% is accepted and setting the limit of P_2 to $1.3 \times 1.5S_m$ means that, in the most unfavourable cases, a membrane plus bending strain of 1.7% and a curvature with a radius equal to 28 times the thickness is accepted.

In fact, the complete expression of the rule as given in RCC-MRx is more general, taking also into account the cases of loadings with secondary membrane stresses and with or without overstress of short duration. Also, when creep is significant the limits on P_{eff} are actually expressed as strain limits, taking into account the effects of creep by means of the creep strain laws of the material. Details on the application of the rules have been given in [5].

4.1.3 Comparison of the $3S_m$, $2S_y$, and efficiency diagram rule for 316L(N) steel.

A direct comparison of the conservatism of the different rules used to prevent ratcheting can be made by representing the allowable operating domains, bounded by the conditions $P_m < S_m$ and $(P_m + P_b) < 1.5S_m$, in the space of the dimensionless ratios $[(P_m/S_m), (\Delta Q/S_m)]$ and $[(P_m + P_b)/(1.5S_m), \Delta Q/(1.5S_m)]$, i.e. scaling the primary and secondary applied loads to the allowable primary stress.

At 20°C (Figure 48), the value of $3S_m$ and $2S_y$ coincide and there is no difference between the two criteria. The efficiency diagram is less conservative in the region of low primary stresses. Using the stress-strain laws for 316L(N) given in appendix A3.1S of RCC-MRx, limiting P_1 to $1.3S_m$ would limit the total deformation to less than 0.10% using the average curve or 0.15% on the minimum curve in the most unfavourable of cases.

Figure 48: Comparison between the 3Sm, 2Sy and efficiency diagram rule for 316L(N) at 20°C.

At 550°C, when creep is significant, the limits for the efficiency diagram rule are no longer expressed in terms of limits on P_{eff} , but as a global limit on the allowable strain depending on the operating time of the component. Still, it is interesting to compare the three criteria assuming the $1.3S_m$ limit on P_{eff} (Figure 49), which can be considered as the equivalent of neglecting creep effects. Using the stress-strain laws for 316L(N) given in A3 of RCC-MRx, limiting P_1 to $1.3S_m$ would limit the total deformation to less than 0.17% using the average curve or 0.89% on the minimum curve in the most unfavorable cases.

Figure 49: Comparison between the 3Sm, 2Sy and efficiency diagram rule for 316L(N) at 550°C.

The comparison between the 3 criteria shows that the theoretical $2S_y$ limit is by definition the most conservative. When comparing the efficiency diagram rule with the $3S_m$ rule, it can be seen that:

-) for values of the ratio (P_m/S_m) higher than ~ 0.7 , i.e. when the primary membrane stress part of the load is high, the efficiency diagram rule is more conservative than the $3S_m$ rule;
-) for low values of the ratio (P_m/S_m), i.e. for low primary membrane stresses, the efficiency diagram rule gives considerable margins with respect to the $3S_m$ limit.

In the region of low primary stresses, the efficiency diagram rule takes into account the fact that progressive deformation is actually difficult to produce. In the region of high primary membrane stresses, which enhance the phenomenon of progressive deformation, the efficiency diagram is

more conservative than the $3S_m$, but the two criteria are very close with differences lower than 30%. At 550°C, for $P_m=S_m$, the efficiency diagram rule is as conservative as the theoretical $2S_y$ limit. Note that when the primary load has also a bending component, the efficiency diagram rule is instead always less conservative than the $3S_m$ (or $2S_y$) criterion (Figure 50).

Figure 50: Comparison between criteria in case of membrane+bending primary stresses for 316L(N) at 20° and 550°C.

It is in fact possible to assess the conservatism of the efficiency diagram rule by comparing different limits for P_{eff} as shown in Figure 51. As the limit on P_{eff} increases, the maximum allowed total deformation, as determined on the stress-strain curves increases but the relation is not linear: the distance between the iso-curves reflects the strain hardening (and cyclic hardening in case of 316L(N)) capability of the material.

Figure 51: Comparison between different limits of P_{eff} – 316L(N) at 550°C.

4.2 Development of a Modified efficiency diagram for P91 steel

Tension-torsion tests on P91 steel specimens at 550°C have been performed in task 7.1 of the MATTER project and are reported in [4]. The results of these tests have been used to verify the validity of the efficiency diagram given in the code by positioning their representative points on the diagram as explained in § 4.1.2.

4.2.1 Tests at high loads

The results of the first tests presented in Table 4 show that for each test, the experimental cumulative strain exceeds the uniform elongation value under maximum load (ϵ_u), with the specimens presenting clear necking before failure. Determination of a stress P_{eff} corresponding to each torsion-tension test is no longer really meaningful because it must be less than S_u and it would then correspond to a strain less than ϵ_u which is the contrary of what was observed. One can also note that values of experimental strains are much greater than predicted values determined using the efficiency diagram of the code. Predicted values do not represent the worst case and are clearly not conservative.

Test id.	Loading Conditions			Predicted values (efficiency diagram)		Experimental values	
	Primary stress (MPa)	Secondary stress variation (MPa)	(P+ΔQ)/3Sm	P_{eff} (MPa)	Cumulative strain (%)	Cumulative strain (%)	P_{eff} (MPa)
B	113.5	1045	3.06	344	0.89	10.7	N/A
C	113.5	941	2.79	327	0.36	4.75	N/A
D	93.6	918	2.68	293	0.18	3.07	N/A
E	74.9	918	2.68	262	0.15	3.88	N/A

Table 4: Results of torsion-tension tests at high loads at 550°C.

4.2.2 Tests at low loads

In order to construct the efficiency diagram as the envelope of the worst cases, the aim is to search for points minimizing the P/P_{eff} ratio. Without ratcheting, P_{eff} is equal to P and thus P/P_{eff} is equal to 1. For a sufficient secondary stress variation ΔQ to obtain ratcheting, the determined effective primary stress P_{eff} becomes higher than the primary stress and then grows when the primary stress P increases. In such conditions the P/P_{eff} ratio becomes less than 1. However, since the value of P_{eff} is bound by S_u and the monotonic stress-strain curve of the 9%Cr is particularly "flat", the P/P_{eff} ratio increases asymptotically towards 1. The P/P_{eff} ratio does not reach its minimal value for the highest values of P .

Therefore, for the remainder of the tests, an attempt was made to reduce the loadings, and in particular the primary stress P , while producing ratcheting in order to reduce the P/P_{eff} ratio and approach lower experimental values. To achieve this, considering the principle that led to the $3S_m$ rule, loads will be taken such that $P + \Delta Q$ is initially close to $1.2 \times (2S_y)$ and then $(2S_y)$.

Table 5 contains details of the loads used and the results of torsion-tension tests at these reduced loads. All tests stopped following the presence of a fatigue crack (observed after disassembly) and not by necking.

Test id.	Loading Conditions			Predicted values (efficiency diagram)		Experimental values		
	Primary stress (MPa)	Secondary stress variation (MPa)	(P+ΔQ)/2Sy	P _{eff} (MPa)	Cumulative strain (%)	Cumulative strain (%)	P _{eff} (MPa)	P/P _{eff}
G	90	709	1.21	252	0.15	0.71	360	0.25
H	114	700	1.24	283	0.17	1.11	362.3	0.31
I	127	640	1.17	285	0.17	1.84	370.3	0.34
J	68	742	1.23	224	0.13	0.54	352.7	0.19
K	155	640	1.21	314	0.24	4.14	374	0.41
L	109	553	1.01	246	0.14	0.62	356.8	0.31
M	83	588	1.02	221	0.13	0.22	299.2	0.28
O	133	526	1.00	264	0.15	0.54	351.5	0.38

Table 5 : Evaluation of effective primary stresses and estimate of cumulative strains (low loads) at 550°C.

4.2.3 Representation of the tests on the efficiency diagram

Table 5 includes the results of tests necessary for the construction of the efficiency diagram. Values of the experimental effective primary stress are estimated from the experimental cumulative strain and the experimental average tension curve. Estimates of “codified” cumulative strains are obtained from the efficiency diagram and the codified average tension curve.

Other tests have been carried out at DMN/SRMA on a servo hydraulic torsion tension testing machine. The temperature of these tests is 450°C. The axial load is chosen to obtain a primary tensile stress of 40, 75 or 100 MPa. The tensile stress-strain curve used for the calculation of the effective primary stress is extract from the Appendix A3.18AS of the RCC-MRx.

In Figure 52, it can be seen that all points representative of the tests in Table 5 are located under the efficiency diagram of RCC-MRx. Therefore, this diagram, in its present form, does not form a lower envelope for tests done with 9%Cr steel at 550°C. Its use for the design would lead to cumulative strains lower than those observed experimentally.

Figure 52 : Representation of the tests in the efficiency diagram

4.2.4 Modified efficiency diagram for P91 steel

On the basis of the results presented in the previous sections, a new efficiency diagram is proposed for P91 and other 9%Cr steel which represents the “worst case” envelope of the obtained result. The equations describing the new diagram have been determined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 SR \leq 0.45 & \quad V = 1 \\
 0.45 < SR \leq 4 & \quad V = 1.1 - \frac{1.15 \times SR^2}{(1 + SR)^2} \\
 SR > 4 & \quad V = \frac{0.98}{SR^{0.72}}
 \end{aligned}$$

The new diagram is shown in Figure 53 and compared with the one used for austenitic steels.

Figure 53: New efficiency diagram proposed for P91 and 9%Cr steels.

4.2.5 Discussion

Figure 54 compares tension behaviours laws of 316L(N) austenitic steel and P91 9%Cr steel. Behaviour laws are divided by Young's modulus for each material at the temperature considered, in order to better identify the difference between hardening of materials and to facilitate the comparison. Laws were extracted from RCC-MRx for 9%Cr (A3.18AS) and 316LN (A3.1S) and the mean experimental law for 9%Cr is also represented. Figure 54 shows that curves for 9%Cr are much flatter and also higher than 316LN curves for values of deformation lower or equal the greater value of uniform elongation at the maximum load (ϵ_u) of 9%Cr steel.

Figure 54 : Comparison of behaviours in tension using cumulative values

Tension curves can be described using a Ramberg – Osgood type description in which the values are in the following form:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma}{E} + K \left(\frac{\sigma}{E} \right)^n = x + Kx^n$$

Use of the variable $x = \sigma/E$ shows that it is the parameters K and n which characterise the hardening and are specific to each material. In the Ramberg – Osgood correlation, ε can be interpreted as the total cumulative strain and σ is therefore the corresponding primary stress (P_{eff}) in the sense of the efficiency diagram.

As we have have seen, for a sufficient secondary stress variation ΔQ the P/P_{eff} ratio becomes less than 1. We can consider different loading configurations ($P, \Delta Q$) so that the value of $\Delta Q/P$ remains constant. When the primary stress P increases the P/P_{eff} ratio decreases and reaches its minimum value $\min_{[P]}(P/P_{eff})$ which is used to define the codified value P_{eff}^{cod} . This situation corresponds to a particular primary stress P to which is associated the primary strain ε_{prim} . The ratcheting is characterised by the cumulative deformation ε_{cum} .

Figure 55 : E/P_{eff} ratios versus cumulative strain

The curves in Figure 55 are the inverse of the curves in Figure 54. Figure 55 shows that the E/P_{eff} curves are dependent of the material. These curves allow the conversion from cumulative strain ϵ_{cum} to the P/P_{eff} ratio by using the primary strain ϵ_{prim} . It can be seen that the E/P_{eff} ratio for 9%Cr is less than the corresponding ratio for 316LN. This relative position remains globally true, even with different cumulative strains. The minimum value of P/P_{eff} for 9%Cr has a good chance of being less than the value obtained by using the 316LN and being quite different, even for cumulative strain that are not too high, for example close to [0.2 % , 04 %].

Another representation of the differences between austenitic and 9%Cr steels with respect to ratcheting behaviour can be made by representing the margins given by the efficiency diagram for P91 at different levels of P_{eff} in the $(P_m/S_m), (Q_m/S_m)$ space as done in §4.1.3 for 316L(N). In Figure 56 it can be seen that the P_{eff} iso-curves are «flatter» and also more closer to each other than those of 316L(N), especially for the higher values of P_{eff} .

The difference between the tension behaviour of 9%Cr steel, with its lower hardening in comparison with austenitic steels, is one factor explaining the difference between the curves shown in Figure 56 and those in Figure 51. The difference in cyclic behaviours, because of the cyclic softening of 9%Cr, is another explanation: the cyclic strain hardening of 316LN steel is conducive to slowing ratcheting and even stabilisation of the cumulative strain during cycling. The adaptation of the efficiency diagram criterion to 9%Cr steels implies therefore not only the development of a new efficiency diagram but also the definition of appropriate limits for P_{eff} .

Figure 56: Comparison between different limits of P_{eff} – P91 at 550°C.

4.3 Application of criterion: limits on P_{eff} for 9%Cr steel

The purpose of using P_{eff} and the efficiency diagram is to introduce a criterion expressed in stress to limit the total (elastic + plastic) ratcheting deformation. The purpose of using the P/P_{eff} ratio is

to obtain a non-dimensional representation of the efficiency diagram. However, the approach uses the tension stress-strain curves specific to each material that can present significant differences, as has just been seen. These differences affect not only the slope of the codified efficiency diagram, but also the limits associated with the criterion.

In order to limit ratcheting, the efficiency diagram criterion defines limits on the effective primary stress P_{eff} that implicitly correspond to strain limitations. These limits are expressed as multiples of the maximum allowable primary stress S_m : $k \cdot S_m$. However, since the stress-strain relation depends on the material, the same values of k lead to different cumulative strains depending on the material. For the same “class” of materials, and for cumulative strains that are considerably lower than the uniform elongation of the material, this difference is usually negligible. This allows to use the same efficiency diagram and the same limitations for all austenitic-type steels contained in RCC-MRx. For 316L(N), the limits on P_{eff} correspond to a maximum cumulative strain of 1% for membrane stresses and 1.7% for membrane plus bending stresses, as explained in §4.1.2.

This is no longer true in case of 9%Cr steels: in particular, with k equal to 1.3 the limit on P_m does not correspond to 1% strain as for austenitic steels, but about 0.1% instead. The material still has an elastic behaviour. Under these conditions, there is no ratcheting phenomenon and therefore no question about limitation of ratcheting. So, while the current efficiency diagram is not conservative for 9%Cr steels, the limits defined in the code appear to be too restrictive.

As seen in §4.1.3, the limits on the efficiency diagram rule for austenitic steel are defined in such a way the criterion is practically as conservative as the theoretical « $2S_y$ » limit when values of the primary membrane stress are close to the allowable S_m . However, using this approach for P91, as it can be seen in Figure 56, would lead to values of the “worst case” cumulative deformation higher than 1.3% which seems excessive considering the uniform elongation of the material at 550°C (close to 2%). Moreover, the limit on P_{eff} would fall in a region where the criterion is very sensible to the variations of P_{eff} . This can be explained by the cyclic softening of the material, which shall therefore be considered when defining the limits to apply to 9%Cr steels.

4.4 Accounting for the cyclic softening of the material

Figure 57 shows the results of two tension-torsion ratcheting tests performed on P91 at 550°C for total loadings $P+\Delta Q$ close to the theoretical $2S_y$ limit. One can see that because of the constant rate of softening of the material there is no stabilization of ratcheting: in fact even at this level of loading, P91 tests show the accumulation of progressive deformation. The «theoretical» $2S_y$ limit needs therefore to be reassessed taking into account the cyclic softening. The limits on the efficiency diagram rule could then be determined on the basis of the «softened» $2S_y$ rule.

Figure 57: Results of tension-torsion ratcheting tests softening and progressive deformation at loadings $\sim 2S_y$

In order to take into account the cyclic softening of the material, it is here proposed to measure the value of the yield strength on the (reduced) cyclic stress-strain curve, instead of the monotonic one. Note that the cyclic-stress strain curve does not correspond to the physical behaviour of the «softened» material but is rather constructed as a set of points obtained from strain controlled fatigue tests by taking the value of the half-life stress variation for a given strain variation. As such, its points do not correspond to any codified property (S_y or S_u) of the material, but nonetheless they give an estimation of the expected degree of softening at a given level of deformation. Moreover, since fatigue criteria impose a margin of 1/20 on the experimentally measured fatigue life of the material, the degree of softening estimated on the cyclic curve is probably too pessimistic, but in any case conservative.

Figure 58 shows the construction used to determine the «softened» value of the yield strength on the cyclic stress-strain curve of the material as given in RCC-MRx. The cyclic curve in the figure has been corrected, to be compared with the monotonic (uniaxial) curve, taking into account that the one given in the code is expressed in terms of the Von Mises equivalents for stress and strain. On the other hand, the curve represents the average behaviour of the material, while limits shall rather be defined with respect to the minimum properties. In order to obtain an equivalent minimum value, it is here proposed to scale the softened S_y value by the same ratio between the minimum and average yield strengths at 550°C:

$$(S_y^{\min})_{soft} = (S_y^{avg})_{soft} \frac{S_y^{\min}}{S_y^{avg}} = 271 \frac{254}{329} = 209 \text{ MPa}$$

Figure 58: Determination of a «softened» S_y limit on the reduced cyclic stress-strain curve.

4.5 Limits on P_{eff} for 9%Cr Steels

Assuming the $2(S_y^{min})_{soft}$ value as the redefined limit for which there is no progressive deformation, the limit on P_{eff} can then be determined by imposing the same conservatism of the two rules when $P_m=S_m$, i.e. in the most penalising condition for the occurrence of progressive deformation (§4.1.3). Since in this case:

$$\overline{P_m} + \overline{\Delta Q} < 2(S_y^{min})_{soft}$$

then, for $P_m=S_m$, we have:

$$S_m + \overline{\Delta Q} = 2(S_y^{min})_{soft}$$

which corresponds, on the new diagram, to a value of the secondary ratio SR equal to:

$$SR_1 = \frac{\overline{\Delta Q}}{S_m} = \frac{2(S_y^{min})_{soft}}{S_m} - 1 = 2.31$$

Using the equations of the efficiency diagram for 9%Cr steel given in § 4.2.4, this would correspond to an efficiency index equal to $v_1=0.54$ and therefore a limit on P_{eff} calculated for membrane stress alone equal to:

$$P_1 = \frac{S_m}{V_1} = \frac{126}{0.54} = 233 \text{ MPa}$$

Or, by expressing this limit as a multiple of S_m :

$$P_1 \leq 1,85 \times S_m$$

Figure 59 show the procedure used for determining the limit of P_{eff} for membrane stress.

Figure 59: Determination of the limit on P_{eff} for primary membrane stress.

The same procedure can be used to determine the limit on P_2 when taking also into account primary membrane plus bending stresses. The maximum allowable primary stress to consider would be in this case $1.5S_m$. This gives:

$$SR_2 = \frac{2(S_y^{\min})_{soft}}{1.5S_m} - 1 = 1.21 \quad ; \quad V_2 = 0.75$$

And then:

$$P_2 = \frac{1.5S_m}{V_2} = \frac{1.5 \times 126}{0.75} = 252 \text{ MPa}$$

The limit on P_2 is then:

$$P_2 \leq 2 \times S_m$$

Note that this limit on P_2 is probably extremely severe, considering also the margins of the efficiency diagram rule with respect to $2S_y$ (or $3S_m$) rule for austenitic steels. However, considering the peculiar ratcheting behaviour of P91 steel, and considering that for values of P_{eff} close to $2S_m$ the efficiency diagram rule is very sensitive to the imposed limit (Figure 56), this conservatism seems justified.

As shown Figure 60 in the assumed limits give, in the most unfavourable cases, a membrane strain of 0.15% and a membrane+bending strain of 0.31%.

Figure 60: Total cumulated deformations for P91 steel at 550°C using the modified efficiency diagram rule.

Note that the proposed criteria do not address the effects of creep. Since in this case deformation is time-dependent, limits for the efficiency diagram rule are expressed in terms of allowable strains rather than allowable stresses, taking into account the combined effects of ratcheting and creep-deformation by means of the creep laws. More experimental tests (for example tension-torsion tests with hold times) are in this case needed, but this is outside the scope of this report.

4.6 Validation of the new efficiency diagram rule for thermal ratcheting.

The new efficiency diagram rule has been developed on the basis of results of tension-torsion tests for mechanical ratcheting. Results obtained in §3 can be used to further validate the proposed rule with respect to thermal ratcheting.

For this purpose, results reported in Table 3 have been represented on the efficiency diagram as shown in Figure 61. It can be seen that all the points are located above the new efficiency diagram proposed for 9Cr steels, while they are below the one defined for austenitic steels. This confirms that the new diagram represents in fact the envelope of the worst cases, i.e. the total deformation predicted by the diagram is conservative and it can effectively be used to limit ratcheting in 9Cr steels

Figure 61: validation of the proposed efficiency diagram rule for thermal ratcheting.

4.7 References for chapter 4

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5 Conclusions

This report constitutes the final deliverable D4.4 – «Recommendation for ratcheting rules for P91 components» of task 4.2 «Ratcheting rules for P91» of the MATTER Project. The objective of this task was to investigate the limits of design rules contained in present-day nuclear Codes & Standards (C&S) with respect to the mechanical behaviour of the ferritic-martensitic 9%Cr steel P91.

The objectives of the work performed in this report were: i) compare the results of numerical simulation with uniaxial-ratcheting experiments performed within the matter project; ii) develop a structural test for the analysis of thermal ratcheting in a configuration relevant for Gen IV reactors vessels and iii) proposal of an improved rule based on the efficiency diagram method in order to effectively limit ratcheting in P91 components.

All objectives have been achieved as presented in the report:

- The isothermal ratcheting behavior of the 9%-Cr-1%-Mo ferritic-martensitic (FM) steel P91 is investigated by uniaxial cyclic loading tests at room temperature (RT) and 550°C. The material under research shows obvious cyclic softening in strain-controlled LCF tests at both temperatures which is found to affect the ratcheting behavior of P91 steel under stress-controlled cyclic loading at both temperatures. A unified visco-plastic deformation model taking into account the complex non-saturating cyclic softening of RAFM steels is further modified to adapt the ratcheting behavior of P91. The model developed is a powerful tool for reliably predicting the material ratcheting behavior of P91 under arbitrary loading conditions. Hence, it can be used to assess the safety margin in new ratcheting design rules for P91 among others for structural ratcheting providing proper verifications and justifications in addition to experiments.
- Aim of the experimental campaign has been the development of a structural test under cyclic thermal loading for the analysis and assessment of the existing ratcheting rules in RCC-MR and for the validation of the updated rules elaborated in the frame of the MATTER Project for P91 components. The experimental campaign has provided also carefully obtained ratcheting data to be used as verification and validation benchmark of inelastic finite elements models. After the description of the experimental facility, the experimental results are presented. Finally an evaluation of the risk of progressive deformation on an elastic basis, according to the RCC-MRx efficiency diagram is given.
- On the basis of the tension-torsion ratcheting tests performed by CEA in task 7.3, the points corresponding to the experimental results have been represented in the space of the variables $SR=\Delta Q/P$ and $V=P/P_{eff}$ in order to determine, as a lower envelope of the most penalising tests, a new efficiency diagram for 9%Cr steels. The adaptation of the efficiency diagram criterion to 9%Cr steels implies however not only the development of a new efficiency diagram but also the definition of appropriate limits for P_{eff} . Particular attention should in this case be given to the peculiar cyclic softening behaviour of the material. By considering the reduced cyclic stress-strain curve, these limits have been proposed by relating the margins given by the new rule to those of a S_y value that takes into account the

softening of the material. Results obtained in experimental campaign to verify ratcheting under cyclic thermal loading have also been used to validate the new efficiency diagram for P91 steel.

Overall, the work performed in this task has allowed a better understanding of ratcheting for P91 steel. The new proposed rule is a modification of the one already included in RCC-MRx and could be integrated in the future editions of the code although it should be completed by taking into account also the effects of creep at high temperatures.